

On the Accuracy of One Formula for the Case of a Stochastic Differential Equation with Jumps

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Random processes with jumps find application in various fields of research, such as economics. Generally researchers are interested in the values of mathematical expectations from processes of this kind. Previously, the author has proposed a formula for the approximate calculation of mathematical expectations from processes defined by a stochastic differential equation containing a process with jumps. In this paper an accuracy estimate is obtained for the earlier proposed formula.

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1. Introduction

Novaday for describing various phenomena observed in the environment and social processes, random processes are increasingly used, including processes with discontinuous trajectories (see, e.g. [1, 2]).

In particular, random processes with paths containing jumps are used in queuing theory. The problem of calculating mathematical expectations of various types from such processes naturally arises. One of the most widely used approaches is the approach based on simulation modeling of processes. This approach requires significant computational resources, since a significant number of trajectories must be used to calculate the value of the mathematical expectation. In a number of cases, it is possible to use an approach based not on modeling trajectories, but on an attempt to construct a weak-type approximation, i.e. an approximation that allows one to estimate some parameters of the process, for example, its moments or a distribution function.

In the paper [5] such an approximation is proposed for the case of a stochastic differential equation with an Ito integral over a process whose

trajectories contain discontinuities, but the paper only describes the process of constructing an approximate formula.

The purpose of this paper is to obtain an assessment of the accuracy of the proposed formula.

Let us remind that the object of research in the paper [5] is a random process given in the form of a stochastic differential equation, which is rewritten below in the integral form:

$$X_t = X_0 + \int_0^t \alpha(X_{s-}, s) ds + \int_0^t \beta(X_{s-}, s) d\tilde{P}_s. \quad (1.1)$$

Here $t \in [0, 1]$, $X_0 \in \mathbb{R}$, $\tilde{P}_t = P_t - \lambda t$ is the compensated Poisson process, $\alpha(X_{s-}, s)$ and $\beta(X_{s-}, s)$ satisfy the following strong solution conditions [3]:

$$|\alpha(y_1, t) - \alpha(y_2, t)|^2 + |\beta(y_1, t) - \beta(y_2, t)|^2 \leq K_1 |y_1 - y_2|^2, \quad (1.2)$$

$$|\alpha(y_1, t)|^2 + |\beta(y_1, t)|^2 \leq K_2 (1 + |y_1|^2), \quad (1.3)$$

where $K_1, K_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ are constants, $y_1, y_2 \in \mathbb{R}$.

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The approximate formula proposed in [5] is intended for calculating a functional of the form $\mathbb{E}G \equiv \mathbb{E}[G(X_{(\cdot)})]$. The notation (\cdot) is used to

indicate, that G can depends on whole trajectory of a solution of the equation (1.1) on $[0, t]$. The formula under study has the form:

$$\mathbb{E}G \approx J(G) = \sum_{j_1, j_2=1}^2 A_{j_1} B_{j_2} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 G[Y_{j_1, j_2}(\cdot, u_1, u_2, u_3)] du_1 du_2 du_3, \quad (1.4)$$

where

$$A_1 + A_2 = 1,$$

$$a_{1,1} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \sqrt{-\frac{A_2}{A_1}} \right), \quad a_{1,2} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \sqrt{-\frac{A_2}{A_1}} \right), \quad a_{2,1} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \sqrt{-\frac{A_1}{A_2}} \right), \quad a_{2,2} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \sqrt{-\frac{A_1}{A_2}} \right),$$

$$B_1 = \frac{1}{2\pi(\mathbb{R})} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + 4\pi(\mathbb{R})}} \right), \quad B_2 = \frac{1}{2\pi(\mathbb{R})} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + 4\pi(\mathbb{R})}} \right),$$

$$b_1 = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 + 4\pi(\mathbb{R})} \right), \quad b_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \sqrt{1 + 4\pi(\mathbb{R})} \right),$$

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{j_1, j_2}(t) &\equiv Y_{j_1, j_2}(t, u_1, u_2, u_3) = X_0 \\ &+ \alpha \left(X_0 + \alpha \left(X_0 + \beta(X_0, u_3) \rho_{j_2}^{(2)}(u_2-, u_3), u_2 \right) \rho_{j_1, 2}^{(1)}(u_1-, u_2) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \beta \left(X_0 + \alpha(X_0, u_2) \rho_{j_1, 2}^{(1)}(u_3-, u_2), u_3 \right) \rho_{j_2}^{(2)}(u_1-, u_3), u_1 \right) \rho_{j_1, 1}^{(1)}(t, u_1) \\ &+ \alpha \left(X_0 + \alpha \left(X_0 + \beta(X_0, u_3) \rho_{j_2}^{(2)}(u_1-, u_3), u_1 \right) \rho_{j_1, 1}^{(1)}(u_2-, u_1) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \beta \left(X_0 + \alpha(X_0, u_1) \rho_{j_1, 1}^{(1)}(u_3-, u_1), u_3 \right) \rho_{j_2}^{(2)}(u_2-, u_3), u_2 \right) \rho_{j_1, 2}^{(1)}(t, u_2) \\ &+ \beta \left(X_0 + \alpha \left(X_0 + \alpha(X_0, u_2) \rho_{j_1, 2}^{(1)}(u_1-, u_2), u_1 \right) \rho_{j_1, 1}^{(1)}(u_3-, u_1) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \alpha \left(X_0 + \alpha(X_0, u_1) \rho_{j_1, 1}^{(1)}(u_2-, u_1), u_2 \right) \rho_{j_1, 2}^{(1)}(u_3-, u_2), u_3 \right) \rho_{j_2}^{(2)}(t, u_3), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\rho_{j_1, k}^{(1)}(s, u_k) = a_{j_1, k} 1_{[u_k, 1]}(s), \quad k = 1, 2, \quad \rho_{j_2}^{(2)}(s, u_3) = b_{j_2} 1_{[u_3, 1]}(s),$$

$$1_{[u_k, 1]}(s) = \begin{cases} 1, & s \in [u_k, 1], \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Here and below we suppose, that G has a Fréchet derivative, which we denotes G' , and

$$|G'(x)| \leq C, \quad (1.5)$$

where $C \in \mathbb{R}$ for any $x \in \mathbb{R}$.

2. Estimating the accuracy of approximate formula

For the convenience of assessing the accuracy of formula (1.4), let us introduce the following notations: $\tilde{X}_t = X_t - X_0$, $\tilde{Y}_{j_1, j_2}(t) = Y_{j_1, j_2}(t) - X_0$ and

$$\hat{X}_t = \int_0^t \alpha(X_0, s) ds + \int_0^t \beta(X_0, s) d\tilde{P}_s$$

At the first let us prove some useful

inequalities.

Proposition 1. $|\mathbb{E}[\hat{X}_t]| \leq \sqrt{K_2(1 + X_0^2)}t^{1/2}$.

PROOF

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathbb{E}[\hat{X}_t]| &= \left| \int_0^t \alpha(X_0, s) ds + \int_0^t \beta(X_0, s) d\tilde{P}_s \right| = \\ & \left| \int_0^t \alpha(X_0, s) ds \right| \leq \left(\int_0^t \alpha^2(X_0, s) ds \right)^{1/2} \leq \\ & \left(\int_0^t K_2(1 + X_0^2) ds \right)^{1/2} = \sqrt{K_2(1 + X_0^2)}t^{1/2}. \end{aligned}$$

■

Proposition 2. *The following inequality is true*

$$\mathbb{E}[(X_t - X_0)^2] \leq \max(t, \lambda)K_2(1 + X_0^2)t + o(t).$$

PROOF

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[(X_t - X_0)^2] &= \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\int_0^t \alpha(X_{s-}, s) ds + \int_0^t \beta(X_{s-}, s) d\tilde{P}_s \right)^2 \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\int_0^t \alpha(X_{s-}, s) ds \right)^2 + \left(\int_0^t \beta(X_{s-}, s) d\tilde{P}_s \right)^2 + 2 \int_0^t \alpha(X_{s-}, s) ds \int_0^t \beta(X_{s-}, s) d\tilde{P}_s \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\int_0^t \alpha(X_{s-}, s) ds \right)^2 \right] + \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\int_0^t \beta(X_{s-}, s) d\tilde{P}_s \right)^2 \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Using Hölder inequality and properties of stochastic Ito integral, the last expression lower or equal to the following expression:

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\left(\left(\int_0^t \alpha^2(X_{s-}, s) ds \right)^{1/2} \left(\int_0^t ds \right)^{1/2} \right)^2 \right] + \int_0^t \mathbb{E}[\beta^2(X_{s-}, s)] d(\lambda s)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \max(t, \lambda) \int_0^t \mathbb{E} [\alpha^2(X_{s-}, s) + \beta^2(X_{s-}, s)] ds \leq \max(t, \lambda) \int_0^t \mathbb{E}[K_2(1 + (X_{s-})^2)] ds \\
&= \max(t, \lambda) \int_0^t K_2(1 + \mathbb{E}[(X_{s-})^2]) ds = \max(t, \lambda) \left(K_2 t + K_2 \int_0^t \mathbb{E}[(X_0 + \tilde{X}_{s-})^2] ds \right) \\
&= \max(t, \lambda) \left(K_2(1 + X_0^2)t + \int_0^t \mathbb{E}[2X_0\tilde{X}_{s-} + (\tilde{X}_{s-})^2] ds \right). \tag{2.1}
\end{aligned}$$

Using assumptions (1.2, 1.3) and make calculations similar to those presented above it is easy to show, that (2.1) is equal to

$$\max(t, \lambda) K_2(1 + X_0^2)t + o(t).$$

Proposition 3. *The following inequality is true*

$$\mathbb{E}[(\tilde{X}_t - \hat{X}_t)^2] \leq \frac{1}{2}(\max(t, \lambda))^2 K_2(1 + X_0^2)t^2 + o(t^2).$$

PROOF

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}[(\tilde{X}_t - \hat{X}_t)^2] &= \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\int_0^t \alpha(X_{s-}, s) ds + \int_0^t \beta(X_{s-}, s) d\tilde{P}_s - \int_0^t \alpha(X_0, s) ds - \int_0^t \beta(X_0, s) d\tilde{P}_s \right)^2 \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\int_0^t \alpha(X_{s-}, s) - \alpha(X_0, s) ds + \int_0^t \beta(X_{s-}, s) - \beta(X_0, s) d\tilde{P}_s \right)^2 \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\int_0^t \alpha(X_{s-}, s) - \alpha(X_0, s) ds \right)^2 + \left(\int_0^t \beta(X_{s-}, s) - \beta(X_0, s) d\tilde{P}_s \right)^2 \right. \\
&\quad \left. + 2 \int_0^t \alpha(X_{s-}, s) - \alpha(X_0, s) ds \int_0^t \beta(X_{s-}, s) - \beta(X_0, s) d\tilde{P}_s \right].
\end{aligned}$$

Using additivity of mathematical expectation and properties of stochastic integral the last expression can be rewritten in the form:

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\left(\int_0^t \alpha(X_{s-}, s) - \alpha(X_0, s) ds \right)^2 + \left(\int_0^t \beta(X_{s-}, s) - \beta(X_0, s) d\tilde{P}_s \right)^2 \right] = (*).$$

Here, by the Hölder inequality, we get

$$\left(\int_0^t \alpha(X_{s-}, s) - \alpha(X_0, s) ds \right)^2 \leq t \int_0^t (\alpha(X_{s-}, s) - \alpha(X_0, s))^2 ds,$$

so

$$(*) \leq \mathbb{E} \left[t \int_0^t (\alpha(X_{s-}, s) - \alpha(X_0, s))^2 ds \right] + \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\int_0^t \beta(X_{s-}, s) - \beta(X_0, s) d\tilde{P}_s \right)^2 \right]$$

by the properties of stochastic Ito integral this expression is equal to:

$$\begin{aligned} & t \int_0^t \mathbb{E} [(\alpha(X_{s-}, s) - \alpha(X_0, s))^2] ds + \int_0^t \mathbb{E} [(\beta(X_{s-}, s) - \beta(X_0, s))^2] d(\lambda s) \\ & \leq \max(t, \lambda) \int_0^t \mathbb{E} [(\alpha(X_{s-}, s) - \alpha(X_0, s))^2 + (\beta(X_{s-}, s) - \beta(X_0, s))^2] ds \end{aligned}$$

according to assumption (1.2)

$$\leq \max(t, \lambda) \int_0^t \mathbb{E} [K_1(X_{s-} - X_0)^2] ds$$

using proposition (2)

$$\leq \max(t, \lambda) K_1 \int_0^t \max(s, \lambda) K_2 (1 + X_0^2) s + o(s) ds \leq \frac{1}{2} (\max(t, \lambda))^2 K_1 K_2 (1 + X_0^2) t^2 + o(t^2).$$

Theorem 1. *The following estimate of the error of the formula (1.4) is valid $|\mathbb{E}[G] - J(G)| = \frac{4}{3} C \sum_{j_1, j_2=1}^2 |A_{j_1}| |B_{j_2}| \sqrt{K_2(1 + X_0^2)} t^{3/2} + o(t^{3/2})$.*

PROOF

Using the Taylor expansion for functional (see, e.g. [4]) we get

$$|\mathbb{E}[G] - J(G)| = \left| \mathbb{E} \left[G(X_0) + \int_0^1 \int_0^t G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{X}_{(\cdot)}) \tilde{X}_s d\tau ds \right] \right|$$

$$- \sum_{j_1, j_2=1}^2 A_{j_1} B_{j_2} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 du_1 du_2 du_3 \left(G(X_0) + \int_0^1 \int_0^t G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{Y}_{j_1, j_2}(\cdot)) \tilde{Y}_{j_1, j_2} d\tau ds \right) \Big|.$$

Here we need to note, that $A_1 + A_2 = 1$ and $B_1 + B_2 = 1$, then the last expression has the form:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_0^1 \int_0^t \mathbb{E} \left[G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{X}_{(\cdot)}) \tilde{X}_s \right] d\tau ds - \sum_{j_1, j_2=1}^2 A_{j_1} B_{j_2} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 du_1 du_2 du_3 \left(\int_0^1 \int_0^t G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{Y}_{j_1, j_2}(\cdot)) \tilde{Y}_{j_1, j_2} d\tau ds \right) \right| \\ &= \left| \int_0^1 \int_0^t \mathbb{E} \left[G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{X}_{(\cdot)}) \tilde{X}_s - G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{X}_{(\cdot)}) \hat{X}_s + G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{X}_{(\cdot)}) \hat{X}_s \right] d\tau ds \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \sum_{j_1, j_2=1}^2 A_{j_1} B_{j_2} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 du_1 du_2 du_3 \left(\int_0^1 \int_0^t G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{Y}_{j_1, j_2}(\cdot)) \tilde{Y}_{j_1, j_2} d\tau ds \right) \right|. \end{aligned}$$

Here we use the properties of A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2 again, then the last equality can be rewritten in the form

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_0^1 \int_0^t d\tau ds \mathbb{E} \left[G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{X}_{(\cdot)}) (\tilde{X}_s - \hat{X}_s) \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \sum_{j_1, j_2=1}^2 A_{j_1} B_{j_2} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 du_1 du_2 du_3 \left(G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{X}_{(\cdot)}) \tilde{X}_s - G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{Y}_{j_1, j_2}(\cdot)) \tilde{Y}_{j_1, j_2}(s) \right) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \left| \int_0^1 \int_0^t d\tau ds \mathbb{E} \left[G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{X}_{(\cdot)}) (\tilde{X}_s - \hat{X}_s) \right] \right| \\ & \quad + \left| \sum_{j_1, j_2=1}^2 A_{j_1} B_{j_2} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 du_1 du_2 du_3 \left(G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{X}_{(\cdot)}) \tilde{X}_s - G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{Y}_{j_1, j_2}(\cdot)) \tilde{Y}_{j_1, j_2}(s) \right) \right| \\ & \leq \int_0^1 \int_0^t \left(\mathbb{E} \left[\left(G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{X}_{(\cdot)}) \right)^2 \right] \right)^{1/2} \left(\mathbb{E} \left[(\tilde{X}_s - \hat{X}_s)^2 \right] \right)^{1/2} d\tau ds \\ & \quad + \left| \int_0^1 \int_0^t d\tau ds \sum_{j_1, j_2=1}^2 A_{j_1} B_{j_2} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 du_1 du_2 du_3 \mathbb{E} \left[G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{X}_{(\cdot)}) \hat{X}_s - G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{Y}_{j_1, j_2}(\cdot)) \hat{X}_s \right] \right| \end{aligned}$$

$$+G'(X_0 + \tau\tilde{Y}_{j_1,j_2}(\cdot))\hat{X}_s - G'(X_0 + \tau\tilde{Y}_{j_1,j_2}(\cdot))\tilde{Y}_{j_1,j_2}(s)\Big] = (**)$$

Here we use the assumption (1.5)

$$(**) \leq C \int_0^t \left(\mathbb{E} \left[(\tilde{X}_s - \hat{X}_s)^2 \right] \right)^{1/2} ds$$

$$+ \left| \int_0^1 \int_0^t d\tau ds \sum_{j_1,j_2=1}^2 A_{j_1} B_{j_2} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 du_1 du_2 du_3 \mathbb{E} \left[\left(G'(X_0 + \tau\tilde{X}_{(\cdot)}) - G'(X_0 + \tau\tilde{Y}_{j_1,j_2}(\cdot)) \right) \hat{X}_s \right] \right|$$

$$+ \left| \int_0^1 \int_0^t d\tau ds \sum_{j_1,j_2=1}^2 A_{j_1} B_{j_2} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 du_1 du_2 du_3 \mathbb{E} \left[G'(X_0 + \tau\tilde{X}_{(\cdot)}) (\hat{X}_s - \tilde{Y}_{j_1,j_2}(s)) \right] \right|.$$

Here we use the proposition 3, then the last expression is lower or equal to the expression:

$$C \int_0^t \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(\max(s, \lambda)^2) K_1 K_2 (1 + X_0^2) s + o(s)} \right) ds$$

$$+ \int_0^1 \int_0^t d\tau ds \sum_{j_1,j_2=1}^2 |A_{j_1}| |B_{j_2}| \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 2C \left| \mathbb{E}[\hat{X}_s] \right| du_1 du_2 du_3$$

$$+ \left| \int_0^1 \int_0^t d\tau ds \sum_{j_1,j_2=1}^2 A_{j_1} B_{j_2} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 G'(X_0 + \tau\tilde{Y}_{j_1,j_2}(\cdot)) \left(\mathbb{E}[\hat{X}_s] - \tilde{Y}_{j_1,j_2}(s) \right) du_1 du_2 du_3 \right|$$

$$\leq \frac{C}{2\sqrt{2}} \max(t, \lambda) \sqrt{K_1 K_2 (1 + X_0^2) t^2 + o(t^2)} + 2C \sum_{j_1,j_2=1}^2 |A_{j_1}| |B_{j_2}| \int_0^t \left| \mathbb{E}[\hat{X}_s] \right| ds$$

$$+ \left| \int_0^1 \int_0^t d\tau ds \sum_{j_1,j_2=1}^2 A_{j_1} B_{j_2} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 G'(X_0 + \tau\tilde{Y}_{j_1,j_2}(\cdot)) \left(\int_0^s \alpha(X_0, v) dv - \tilde{Y}_{j_1,j_2}(s) \right) du_1 du_2 du_3 \right|$$

$$\leq \frac{C}{2\sqrt{2}} \max(t, \lambda) \sqrt{K_1 K_2 (1 + X_0^2) t^2 + o(t^2)} + 2C \sum_{j_1,j_2=1}^2 |A_{j_1}| |B_{j_2}| \sqrt{K_2 (1 + X_0^2)} \frac{2}{3} t^{3/2} + o(t^{3/2})$$

$$+ \sum_{j_1,j_2=1}^2 |A_{j_1}| |B_{j_2}| C \left| \int_0^t \int_0^s \alpha(X_0, v) dv ds \right|$$

$$+ \left| \int_0^1 \int_0^t d\tau ds \sum_{j_1, j_2=1}^2 A_{j_1} B_{j_2} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 G'(X_0 + \tau \tilde{Y}_{j_1, j_2}(\cdot)) \tilde{Y}_{j_1, j_2}(s) du_1 du_2 du_3 \right|.$$

Using transformations similar to those given above, we get for the last expression:

$$\frac{4}{3} C \sum_{j_1, j_2=1}^2 |A_{j_1}| |B_{j_2}| \sqrt{K_2(1 + X_0^2)} t^{3/2} + o(t^{3/2}),$$

so the theorem was proved. ■

3. Conclusion

This paper provides an assessment of the accuracy of the formula (1.4) proposed in [5].

It should be noted that the assessment depends on the coefficients specified by the user. The obtained estimate is quite general and can be improved if additional conditions are specified for the functional to which this formula will be applied.

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